

Motor impairment estimates via touchscreen typing dynamics towards Parkinson's disease detection from data harvested in-the-wild

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative disorder with early non-motor/motor symptoms
4 that may evade clinical detection for years after the disease onset due to their mildness and slow
5 progression. Digital health tools that process densely sampled data streams from the daily human-
6 mobile interaction can objectify the monitoring of behavioral patterns that change due to the
7 appearance of early PD-related signs. In this context, touchscreens can capture micro-movements
8 of fingers during natural typing; an unsupervised activity of high frequency that can reveal
9 insights for users' fine-motor handling and identify motor impairment. Subjects' typing dynamics
10 related to their fine-motor skills decline, unobtrusively captured from a mobile touchscreen, were
11 recently explored in-the-clinic assessment to classify early PD patients and controls. In this
12 study, estimation of individual fine motor impairment severity scores is employed to interpret
13 the footprint of specific underlying symptoms (such as brady-/hypokinesia (B/H-K) and rigidity
14 (R)) to keystroke dynamics that cause group-wise variations. Regression models are employed
15 for each fine-motor symptom, by exploiting features from keystroke dynamics sequences from
16 in-the-clinic data captured from 18 early PD patients and 15 healthy controls. Results show that R
17 and B/H-K UPDRS Part III single items scores can be predicted with an accuracy of 78% and 70%
18 respectively. The generalization power of these trained regressors derived from in-the-clinic data
19 was further tested in a PD screening problem using data harvested in-the-wild for a longitudinal
20 period of time ($mean \pm std : 7 \pm 14$ weeks) via a dedicated smartphone application for unobtrusive

21 sensing of their routine smartphone typing. From a pool of 210 active users, data from 13 self-
22 reported PD patients and 35 controls were selected based on demographics matching with the
23 ones in-the-clinic setting. The results have shown that the estimated index achieve $\{0.84 (R), 0.80$
24 $(B/H-K)\}$ ROC AUC, respectively, with $\{sensitivity/specificity : 0.77/0.8 (R), 0.92/0.63 (B/H-$
25 $K)\}$, on classifying PD and controls in-the-wild setting. Apparently, the proposed approach
26 constitutes a step forward to unobtrusive remote screening and detection of specific early PD
27 signs from mobile-based human-computer interaction, introduces an interpretable methodology
28 for the medical community and contributes to the continuous improvement of deployed tools and
29 technologies in-the-wild.

30

31 **Keywords:** fine motor skills, Parkinson's Disease, keystroke dynamics, unobtrusive monitoring, data in-the-wild, machine learning,
32 digital medicine

1 INTRODUCTION

33 Parkinson's Disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disorder after Alzheimer's Disease
34 (Shulman et al. (2011)) with a wide clinical spectrum of motor and non-motor symptoms (Chaudhuri et al.
35 (2006)), which are mild in the early stages and are causing progressive disability at the later ones. The
36 underlying neuropathological process is preceding the onset of relevant PD motor symptoms up to decades,
37 leaving the disease undiagnosed for years (Hawkes et al. (2010); Schrag et al. (2015)). PD is creating
38 significant impact on patients' quality of life, that, in part, is caused by a wide variety of motor impairments,
39 such as brady-/hypokinesia (B/H-K) and rigidity (R), being, yet, less evident for the person concerned
40 due to their mildness in the early stages of the disease. Furthermore, degradation in motor function is
41 reflected to patient's motor behavioral patterns, e.g., fine motor movements, speed of reflex movements
42 and intermittent tremor. Diagnosis of PD is made by a movement disorders specialist who assesses, usually
43 clinically, the patient's overall condition using questionnaires and standardized scales, such as the Unified
44 Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (Fahn et al. (1987)). UPRDS Part-III (Goetz et al. (2008)) consists of 14
45 single items qualitatively measuring the range of PD motor symptomatology, evaluated by experts during
46 the examination of specific tasks.

47 Objective and frequent evaluation with quantitative measures can assist the clinical decision making
48 process on PD diagnosis and patients' monitoring. Nevertheless, in clinical examination, subject's self-
49 reports are frequently involved as a source of information, subjected to the experience of the physician
50 to assess the severity of the PD symptoms. Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-based
51 solutions (Mellone et al. (2012)) and plethora of related data can assist the relevant stakeholders to better
52 understand the disease's impact on daily habits, even in the early stages, as well as patient's response to
53 drug therapy. An emerging field of ICT where large-scale data streams are acquired from users' habitual
54 patterns is human-mobile interaction. The latter can reveal everyday information that could be transformed
55 to useful behavioral indices, built in a dynamic and personalized way across the time of interaction. Design
56 of digital monitoring tools for PD with diagnostic value has been a research field with a great variety
57 of applications, due to the wide spectrum of PD clinical symptoms. Efforts processing data streams as
58 captured from ICT devices, have proven to be robust in distinguishing populations facing motor symptoms
59 from healthy ones, in different sub-tasks in-the-clinic assessment, such as voice (Orozco-Arroyave et al.
60 (2016)), gait or tremor (Abdulhay et al. (2018)).

61 Digital health solutions with potential transferability to real-life environments (in-the-wild) is a
62 challenging step to capture both useful disease indicators and achieve long-term adherence. Bot et al.
63 (2016) were the first ones that reported a large-scale smartphone-based PD-related study, namely mPower,
64 with over 9000 participants (both PD and healthy users), aiming remote PD screening by suggesting
65 patients to perform designed digitized tests to assess motor-functionalities and self-reported questionnaires.
66 However, drop out rates highlighted that the specific tests are not viable for long term user engagement.
67 Moreover, Zhan et al. (2018) have recently used a mobile application to assess longitudinal PD patients
68 via tests on five scheduled scenarios, and by using sensorial data analysis, they proposed an aggregated
69 index that was correlated with the total UPDRS Part III score. Although both aforementioned studies paved
70 the way for smartphone-based PD assessment, they included the requirement of users' active interaction
71 with the mobile application. This requirement, however, is a non-resilient factor for avoiding drop outs
72 and subjects are possibly subjected to Hawthorne effect (Monahan and Fisher (2010)). Non-obtrusive and
73 passive sensing of data could overcome the latter barriers in designing such monitoring tools. Such an
74 example is a recent study (Arroyo-Gallego et al. (2018)) designed to unobtrusively perform data collection
75 from keystroke typing on physical keyboard on subjects' PCs, in order to detect subjects with PD by using
76 a machine learning approach. In fact, a numerical index was produced that related hold time keystrokes to
77 the total UPDRS Part-III score. A possible drawback of this approach (Giancardo et al. (2016)), was the
78 use of the total UPDRS Part-III score as the regression target as it encapsulates both relevant (e.g., B/H-K)
79 and irrelevant (e.g., voice degradation, gait) items with keystroke typing and fine-motor movement. The
80 produced index performed 0.83 Area Under Curve (AUC) of the Receiving Operating Characteristic (ROC)
81 with 0.77/0.72 sensitivity/specificity in classifying PD patients and healthy users, when they were typing in-
82 the-clinic setting, and 0.76 AUC and sensitivity/specificity of 0.73/0.69 during the remote at-home-setting
83 assessment.

84 Fine-motor skills decline can also be detected from typing patterns on mobile touchscreen as derived
85 from recent similar works on typing pattern analysis on mobile touchscreen (Iakovakis et al. (2018);
86 Arroyo-Gallego et al. (2017)), during in-the-clinic experiments. In our latest study, we proposed a feature
87 vector representation of enriched keystroke information and a two-stage machine learning-based pipeline
88 to process multiple typing sessions as captured from mobile touchscreen, performing 0.92 AUC with
89 0.82/0.81 sensitivity/specificity on early PD and healthy subject's classification. Subjects typed multiple
90 typing sessions during in-the-clinic medical examination, the derived typing sequences were analyzed
91 and the study findings resulted in four keystroke features with high discriminative power, and a plausible
92 connection with symptoms.

93 Motivated by the aforementioned, the current study steps further by analyzing keystroke information
94 with respect to specific motor symptoms that are possibly causing the variations to PD patients' typing
95 patterns. The analysis direction is aiming to increase the interpretation of the produced indexes, by targeting
96 the UPDRS Part III single item scores that are related to the PD fine motor symptoms. The first part
97 of this study is the exploitation of the best performing features from mobile touchscreen typing in the
98 binary setting (control or PD patient), as predictors of specific UPDRS Part III single items, in order to
99 predict each symptoms' severity in the standardized medical scale, so to be easily interpreted by medical
100 experts. From a methodological point of view, by employing regression models, numerical indexes were
101 produced, which describe the severity of the motor symptomatology on typing kinetics, and tested with a
102 leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) validation of symptom's severity estimation, using keystroke features as
103 dependent variables; the target variables were the UPDRS Part III single item scores of each symptom. The
104 conceptualization of this analysis direction was reinforced from the correlation results between both the

105 employed features and the specific UPDRS Part III single items, and the variation that the symptoms had
106 plausibly caused to keystroke distribution coming from PD patients.

107 Furthermore, the second contribution of the present work is the testing of the generalization power of
108 these trained regressors from the in-the-clinic to the in-the-wild data analysis. Mobile touchscreen typing
109 data were unobtrusively captured from users via a dedicated smartphone application. More specifically, the
110 employment of the developed models in-the-wild setting was used to investigate further their diagnostic
111 performance and their time response to a longitudinal manner. Multi modal data were collected through a
112 developed research data donation application (i-Prognosis (2017)), and a third-party keyboard was included
113 to capture keystroke dynamics from routine typing. The variance and noise induced to the data from the
114 daily activities in the uncontrolled setting, is a real-life challenge when screening in an unobtrusive manner.
115 However, touchscreen typing is a high-frequent activity and usually is an activity with cognitive attention;
116 factors that contribute to the retainment of user's specific patterns in keystroke dynamics across time.

117 The present work is in line with the efforts towards predictive analytics approaches, both in-the-clinic
118 and in-the-wild data analysis, in capturing PD-related early signs. This could potentially add in building an
119 effective PD prediction system, taking into consideration the pragmatic conditions of everyday living, for
120 automatic remote inference and recommendation of PD diagnosis and management.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

121 Based on the findings of our previous work (Iakovakis et al. (2018)), this study exploits the most
122 discriminative features as the representation of typing patterns on mobile touchscreen, and make use
123 of regression models to estimate individual UPDRS Part III single items scores relevant to fine-motor
124 impairment. As it is depicted in Figure 1, the selected features are used as the independent variables for
125 estimating the symptoms' severity which are the UPDRS Part III single items scores, used as the target
126 variables for the training of the different regression models. A LOSO evaluation with nested cross validation
127 for regressors' optimization scheme is used in the development set (DSet) in-the-clinic (**Figure 1A**), to
128 identify the models and symptoms that can be predicted, and the generalization of the methods' is tested
129 in-the-wild scenario (**Figure 1B**). The estimators are evaluated in their diagnostic properties using ROC
130 based performance in the binary setting of classifying PD and healthy users. The goal of this employment
131 is to investigate the diagnostic properties of the method as well as the transferability potential.

132 2.1 Data collection

133 2.1.1 In-the-clinic data

134 The DSet consisted of data acquired from 33 subjects who provided data on a day of visit at the clinic.
135 The collection protocol included a typing experiment of multiple text excerpts on smartphones and a
136 clinical evaluation. These data were logged in a spreadsheet file and mapped to the subjects' coded IDs
137 by the neurologist. The specific UPDRS Part III single item scores used in the regression analysis were
138 item 31/ 21/ 22/ 23 for Bradykinesia-Hypokinesia/ Tremor/ Rigidity/ Finger Taps, respectively. The DSet
139 study protocol was approved by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece (Bioethics Committee
140 of Medical School, approval no. 359/3.4.17). Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects
141 prior to their participation in the study and the procedures carried out were according to institutional
142 and international guidelines on research studies involving adult human beings. Subjects held the right
143 to withdraw from the procedure at any time, without providing any justification. Recruitment and study
144 procedures were carried out according to institutional and international guidelines on research involving

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the methodological steps referring to: (A) the DSet keystroke data from touchscreen typing captured in-the-clinic setting and (B) the extension of the best resulted models from the DSet to the GData. LOSO-based training/testing is used to evaluate which regressor can achieve better estimation of motor symptoms via the use of keystroke dynamics features as inputs and UPDRS Part III single item scores as targets. The regressors that efficiently capture the scale of symptoms severity are used in-the-wild setting for subjects characterization as PD or control.

145 adult human beings. PD patients under medication (14) has mean/std Levadopa equivalent dose of 237/156,
 146 and were asked to refrain from taking it for at least eight hours before their visit. More detailed information
 147 about the dataset acquisition and study cohort can be found in Iakovakis et al. (2018).

148 2.1.2 In-the-wild data

149 The data captured in-the-wild (GData) were collected by the i-PROGNOSIS remote data collection
 150 study (GData study). Subjects from four countries across EU contributed pseudo-anonymised multi modal
 151 data remotely (e.g., voice, handling) via downloading the mobile application from Google Play store
 152 and enrolling in the study. The application provides information regarding the study details on its first
 153 launch and gives subjects the option to communicate with medical representatives in each country in
 154 case of additional questions. An electronic informed consent was obtained from all subjects enrolled,
 155 within the smartphone application, by digitally signing a dated consent form. Due to the remote nature
 156 of the study, obtaining written consent was impractical. Subjects held the right to withdraw from the
 157 procedure at any time via the available option within the application and even request the deletion of the
 158 collected data. Subjects of GData have the option to use the third-party keyboard included in the application
 159 named iPrognosis App, as to capture the keystroke dynamics during their routine typing activities. All the
 160 experimental and ethical protocols were approved by Ethik-Kommission an der Technischen Universität
 161 Dresden, Dresden, Germany (EK 44022017), Greece, Bioethics Committee of the Aristotle University of
 162 Thessaloniki Medical School, Thessaloniki, Greece (359/3.4.17), Portugal Conselho de Ética, Faculdade
 163 de Motricidade Humana, Lisbon, Portugal (CEFMH 17/2017), and United Kingdom London, Dulwich
 164 Research Ethics Committee (17/LO/0909).

165 Two hundred and ten total users provided 42812 typing sessions (mean/std 204/460 typing sessions
 166 per user). However, only subjects who self-reported to be aged between 48 years and 80 years old were
 167 included in the analysis in order to be in the same age group with the subjects in the DSet, resulting in a
 168 total of 48 subjects.

169 2.1.3 Data capturing

170 The application for capturing keystroke-related data includes a custom software keyboard developed for
 171 the Android Operating System (OS) by three authors (D. I., S. H. and V. H.). The users have to enable the
 172 software keyboard after the application installation and set it as the default input method. Subjects of the
 173 in-the-clinic assessment performed the typing task using the custom keyboard and a common smartphone
 174 provided by the authors, whereas in-the-wild subjects used the keyboard with their own mobile devices. In
 175 the background, a class of the software keyboard captured the timestamps of press and release touch events
 176 for each key tap, as well as the normalised pressure (0.000-1.000) on each press event as outputted by the
 177 OS. Each key tap was also flagged as a long-press event, corresponding to deliberate special keyboard
 178 actions, or not. The characters typed were not captured, as the context of what is being typed is not required
 179 for the analysis, rendering our data collection process privacy-aware. For each typing session (keyboard
 180 shown and afterwards hidden, with at least one key tap in the meantime), sequences of captured data were
 181 stored in JSON format and were indexed as database entry in a local SQLite database, available only to the
 182 application. The application periodically transmitted database entries to a remote cloud server (Microsoft
 183 Azure) when the user's device was connected to Wi-Fi and charging. Each entry was accompanied by a
 184 unique coded ID of the user to ensure privacy.

185 2.2 Feature extraction and regression analysis

186 2.2.1 Keystroke dynamic features

187 The derivatives of time-stamp sequences of touchscreen key press t_n^p and release t_n^r produce the so-
 188 called hold time (HT) and flight time sequences (FT). The HT sequences, containing values of HTs
 189 $HT_n = t_n^r - t_n^p, n = 1, 2, \dots, N$, i.e., the differences between the time-stamp a key was released and the
 190 time-stamp the key was pressed, are pre-processed, in order to discard deliberate long-presses. Similarly,
 191 the FT sequences, containing values of FTs $FT_n = t_{n+1}^p - t_n^r, n=1, 2, \dots, N-1$, i.e., the differences between
 192 the time-stamp a key is pressed and the time-stamp the previous key was released, were also pre-processed
 193 to minimize the effect of typing dexterity and subjective factors. In particular, the filtering process included
 194 an upper bound of 3s for sequence elements, a normalization procedure per typing session and a conditional
 195 filtering step to the produced normalized FT (NFT) sequences, as follows:

$$NFT_n = FT_n - \overline{FT_n}, NFT_n \in [-1.27, 1.7]s, n = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1. \quad (1)$$

196 Each typing session is represented by a feature vector consisting of mean of mean μ of Hold time (HT),
 197 mean of standard deviation (σ) of HT as long as skewness S of normalized flight times, as derived by
 198 aggregating non-overlapping windows of 15 (s) of keystroke sequences:

$$X = \{HT\bar{\mu}, HT\bar{\sigma}, NFT\bar{S}\} \quad (2)$$

199 The aforementioned typing features are drawn from our previous study Iakovakis et al. (2018), in which
 200 statistical representations of sequences of HT, FT and normalized pressure (NP) values were examined

201 in-the-clinic data. However, in some cases, operational system implementations do not provide the value of
202 NP, therefore the NP-related feature was omitted from in-the-wild data analysis, as no consistency in same
203 smartphone devices was secured across the GData users.

204 2.2.2 Regression

205 For each of the UPDRS Part III items related to upper-extremity fine-motor symptoms, scores can be
206 directly associated with the symptom severity, a regression model (transformation) was trained/tested,
207 under a leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) scheme with inner cross validation for regressors' parameters
208 optimization, to estimate the score of the corresponding item (target) on a typing session level. The total
209 275 typing sessions of DSet were assigned with the quantized target score of UPDRS Part III single
210 items for each subject. By design, UPDRS scores (integer between 0-4) were quantized. Quantization
211 levels span the severity of the underlying symptom with the lowest value (0) denoting a normal behavior,
212 values between (0-2) exhibiting mild symptoms, and values from 3 up to 4 severe impairment or inability.
213 Regression can granularize the target domain and provide an index of higher resolution, based on the
214 continuous input predictors (i.e., the keystroke dynamics features of X). The UPDRS single items scores
215 under investigation are B/H-K (B), tremor of right/left hand (T_r/T_l), rigidity (R) of right/left hand (R_r/R_l)
216 and alternative finger tapping of right/left (AFT_r/AFT_l). In general, regression models involve: (a) the
217 unknown parameters, denoted as β , (b) the independent variables, X and the dependent variable, Y . In
218 our case, the regression analysis aims to investigate if the regressors f_i can approximate the scale of Y_i -th
219 symptom's severity on each subject, i.e.:

$$Y_i \approx f_i(X; \beta), i \in \{B, T_r, T_l, R_r, R_l, AFT_r, AFT_l\} \quad (3)$$

220 An inner cross validation loop is used to optimize the β parameters of the different models under test.
221 The models that were evaluated for the regression training were Support-Vector-Regression (Smola and
222 Schölkopf (2004)), Lasso and Ridge Regression (Tibshirani (1996)), Random Forests (Liaw and Wiener
223 (2002)), and Bagging of Linear Regressors (Breiman (1996)). We evaluated the accuracy of each regressor
224 on a subject level to measure the ability to capture the scale of the severity, as long as the test error,
225 by employing the Pearson's correlation coefficient and the mean absolute error (MAE). The regression
226 analysis was applied in-the-clinic data and the learned functions f_i that can explain a significant part of the
227 underlying symptom and the mean absolute test error is below 0.5 (the half distance between the quantized
228 scores), were further evaluated in-the-wild setting, as explained in the succeeding section.

229 2.3 Regression models exploitation in-the-wild

230 Each subject $K_d \in G$, where G is denoted the set of GData subjects, has produced a sequence of s_j typing
231 sessions, and a corresponding feature vector Xs_j where $j \in \{1, \dots, n_d\}$ is the total number of sessions for
232 subject K_d .

233 2.3.1 Session level analysis

234 The feature extraction pipeline of typing session as captured in-the-wild (GData), depicted in **Figure2A**,
235 includes a post-hoc filtering component that discards recordings with less than eight keystrokes, to foster
236 the statistical validity of the subsequent feature extraction. Therefore, each typing session is subjected to a
237 windowing process that discards windows with less than four keystrokes to be consistent with the DSet
238 processing pipeline. The values of Xs_j are computed via aggregation across valid windows. Each session

Figure 2. Procedural pipeline for processing GData (A) per typing session and (B) per subject. Typing sessions with at least eight keystrokes are considered valid for processing, whereas the rest are omitted. The keystroke dynamics consist of hold time (HT) and flight time (FT) sequences and are both split by non-overlapping 15s windows (W_j). Only windows with at least four keystrokes within the 15s interval are used further in order to extract features by computing the mean feature distribution for the valid corresponding windows. Each subject K_d has contributed typing features that are grouped by a time window δ , which is considered valid if contains more than 10 sessions. Each session X_j^d is transformed with a learned mapping $f_k, k \in B/H - K, R$ which was previously trained on a the D_{Set} , computes a single numerical score from each typing session. An aggregation mechanism $F(\cdot)$ is applied to each time window δ to characterize subject's time window contribution over time.

239 is represented by a feature vector X_j^d for the subject $K_d \in G$. Three features are extracted from each valid
 240 typing session from GData and the learned mappings (f_i) are applied to each session.

241 2.3.2 Subject level analysis

242 From a subject's perspective, an aggregation mechanism $F(\cdot)$ over the estimates $f_i(X_{S_j})$ that belongs to
 243 a period of time δ , is used to characterize the subject's distribution during this time period (see **Figure 2B**).
 244 Each time window δ can contain a different number of estimates associated with a time-stamp t . Subject's
 245 contribution with less than 10 valid feature vectors X_j^d during the period δ is omitted from the analysis, in
 246 order for the δ to contain enough number of typing sessions. In the current context of analysis, we examine
 247 the median as the aggregation mechanism $F(\cdot)$ to get the most representative sample from the distribution.
 248 Moreover, two time windows $\delta \in \{1, 52\}$ weeks are used for validating the discrimination power of the
 249 estimators. In particular, the time frame of a week ($\delta = 1$) is chosen to include all patterns and habits that
 250 can vary during a week (micro-level), whereas all 52 weeks ($\delta = 52$) are set as the global time frame of the
 251 analysis for a macro-level perspective.

252 2.3.3 PD classification performance evaluation

253 The motor estimates resulted from the aforementioned subject-level analysis, are evaluated in the binary
 254 classification performance (PD vs. control), by estimating the area under curve (AUC) of the ROC curve.
 255 ROC based performance of the indexes discrimination power is computed with Confidence Interval (CI)

Figure 3. Box plots of keystroke dynamic variables (FT and HT) distributions when comparing the two data capturing settings (DSet and GData).

256 with 1,000 bootstraps. Additionally, the sensitivity/specificity metrics, corresponding to the optimal ROC-
 257 based cut-off point (decision threshold), are estimated by maximizing the Youden Index (Fluss et al.
 258 (2005)), under the assumption that costs for false positives and false negatives are equal.

259 2.3.4 Statistical Analysis

260 Logistic regression tests using the subject status (PD or control) as dependent variable and symptoms
 261 predictions, sex, age, years of education and usability of smartphones as independent variables, are
 262 performed for statistical significance evaluation of the variables discrimination power. The two groups (PD
 263 and controls) of the GData setting are tested in terms of demographics using a two-sided Mann-Whitney U
 264 test. Moreover, a two-sided Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the null hypothesis that two samples are drawn
 265 from the same continuous distribution is used to examine the statistically significant difference of the
 266 raw keystroke dynamics between PD and controls. Statistically significant difference is set at the level of
 267 $p < 0.05$.

3 RESULTS

268 3.1 Keystroke dynamics distributions

269 In **Figure 3**, the raw keystroke dynamics variables under investigation are compared with respect to their
 270 distribution as drawn from the DSet and the GData settings. From this figure, a clear similarity in the trend
 271 between the two settings can be observed. Moreover, both HT and FT values, are statistically different
 272 ($p < 0.001$) for group-wise comparisons of PD and controls in the two settings. This justifies the initial
 273 assumption of the robustness of the proposed approach to transfer knowledge from analysis in-the-clinic to
 274 the one in-the-wild, as described below.

275 Table 1 here

Figure 4. Regression estimates (green dots) of LOSO experiment using keystroke dynamic features and UPDRS Part III single items scores. The median of the predicted values distribution across the typing session predictions are also plotted per subject. Moreover, error bars of height ± 0.5 are superimposed to show if the symptom estimation lies within the span of the physician’s score.

276 3.2 In-the-clinic setting

277 From the LOSO analysis results it was found that the best performing regression models achieved 0.83
 278 (0.39), 0.69 (0.41) and 0.68 (0.55) Pearson’s correlation coefficient (MAE) for predicting dominant-hand
 279 R, B/H-K and right-handed finger tapping, respectively. As MAE was greater than 0.5 for the case of
 280 right-handed finger tapping, overlapping the quantized levels of UPDRS Part III scores, dominant hand R
 281 and B/H-K were only involved in the consequent analysis. The predictions of the latter two symptoms and
 282 the UPDRS Part III single item scores are visualized in **Figure 4**. In particular, the dominant-hand R and
 283 B/H-K median predicted scores are depicted along with the medical scores, using error-bars of 0.5 height.
 284 The produced indexes achieve 78% and 70% in predicting the quantized UPDRS medical scores on R and
 285 B/H-K scores during the LOSO experiment, respectively. The rest UPDRS single items ($T_{l/r}$, R_l , AFT_l)
 286 related to motor activity can not be predicted from the keystroke features. This is due to the low Pearson’s
 287 correlation coefficient values (< 0.35), which are probably caused by the use of dominant hand during
 288 typing (all of them were right-handed) and the possible subtle relation of finger movement coordination
 289 with hand tremor (see also 4).

290 Table 2 here

291 3.3 In-the-wild setting

292 As it was mentioned in the 2.1, GData subjects have matched demographic characteristics of the ones
 293 participated in DSet, in order to avoid any inhomogeneity across the two data settings, after appropriate
 294 subject filtering process. Moreover, results from the statistical analysis tests, tabulated in **Table 1**, show
 295 that data from a PD patients’ and a healthy controls’ group, are matched in terms of demographics.
 296 Furthermore, ROC curves of the the two estimated indexes estimated for each subject are depicted in

Figure 5. Classification performance of the median predicted estimates of R and B/H-K during the time frame of $\delta = 52$. ROC curves demonstrating the classification performance of the proposed models for estimating individual motor symptoms on the GData (13 PD patients/35 controls). Solid lines represent the mean ROC curve, while shadowed areas delimit the 95% confidence intervals, computed over 1,000 bootstraps. From the ROC curves the corresponding AUC values are for the R 0.84 (0.75/0.93 is the 95%CI) and for the B/H-K is 0.80 (0.7/0.92 is the 95%CI), respectively.

297 **Figure 5**, considering as time-frame $\delta = 52$ weeks. In particular, estimation of R achieves 0.84 (0.75/0.93
 298 is the 95%CI) AUC with 0.77/0.8 sensitivity/specificity and 0.79 accuracy, where the estimation of B/H-K
 299 achieves 0.80 (0.7/0.92 is the 95%CI) AUC with 0.92/0.63 sensitivity/specificity and 0.70 accuracy in
 300 the GData cohort (more diagnostic properties are tabulated in 2). In addition, when assessing diagnostic
 301 properties of subjects' contribution in time frame ($\delta = 1week$), the indexes achieve lower discrimination
 302 performance with 0.80 AUC for R with 0.82/0.65 sensitivity/specificity and 0.78 AUC with 0.86/0.60
 303 sensitivity/specificity for B/H-K. Finally, statistical significance discriminative performance of the estimated
 304 indexes was found ($p < 0.001$) with logistic regression models including gender, age, years of education
 305 and mobile usability time as co-variates, achieving $p < 0.001$, where the other dependent variables (see
 306 2.3.4) did not show any statistical significance.

4 DISCUSSION

307 Digital Health is an emerging field that could enhance disease detection and management via the realization
308 of objective and accessible tools that could quantify behavioral characteristics. Unobtrusive capturing of
309 data via the natural interaction with digital devices is a key factor of digital tools' design to meet the need
310 of long-adherence. User's habitual patterns are influenced by motor symptoms, even in the early stage
311 of PD where the motor manifestation is subtle. The underlying behavior can be detected via algorithmic
312 transformation of high frequency sampled data streams to useful medical indicators, that can be interpreted
313 from physicians and assist the longitudinal process of passive monitoring, diagnosis and treatment. The
314 current study design aims to amalgamate the aforementioned requirements, while the results contribute
315 to the interpretation and the real life transferability of the developed methods, by exploiting keystroke
316 dynamics during routine typing on mobile touchscreen, a fine-motor activity which is of high frequency due
317 to the booming of mobile technology (Sarwar and Soomro (2013)). A machine learning-based estimation
318 of dominant-hand rigidity and bradykinesia/hypokinesia severity is employed using captured keystroke
319 typing features.

320 The individual items of R and B/H-K, related to fine-motor skills decline in PD, are used as regression
321 targets to provide a granular data driven estimation about the specific fine motor symptom, which is more
322 interpretable than a high-level label for the subject (e.g., a binary label or total UPDRS Part III single item
323 score). The regression results show that dominant-hand R and B/H-K predictions achieve a low test error
324 and can sufficiently capture the severity of symptom. Hand tremor and non-dominant hand UPDRS Part III
325 single item scores, however, could not be predicted during the proposed analysis, which resulted in low
326 correlation coefficients (<0.35). The latter can be explained by the nature of the finger typing information,
327 which can be disentangled to the finger reflexes of pressing the keys (can expressed via HT) and the finger
328 movements across the digital screen (FT); actions that can be influenced by R and B/H-K but not directly
329 from tremor. In addition, PD patients were at the early stage of the disease and their UPDRS Part III single
330 item scores were in the lower scales 0 – 2 for both symptoms. The latter reinforces the added value of the
331 results towards capturing PD specific fine-motor impairment at the early stage of the disease, where the
332 symptoms are mild. Moreover, the expansion of the developed in-the-clinic method to the uncontrolled
333 setting in-the-wild constitutes a step towards remote passive monitoring of users' fine-motor symptoms.
334 The unobtrusive capturing of GData containing more than 40.000 typing sessions (mean/std: 204/406 per
335 subject) from 210 total users (mean/std weeks of each subject's data contribution: 7/14), highlights the
336 positive effect of the unobtrusive data collection in the long-term adherence. This overcomes the dropouts
337 seen in recent smartphone-based studies for PD, which require active user's involvement (Bot et al. (2016);
338 Zhan et al. (2018)).

339 The diagnostic properties of the produced indexes achieved up to 0.8/0.77 sensitivity/specificity on
340 classifying PD and healthy subjects in the wild setting, when aggregating for the whole time period of data
341 contribution, which matches the satisfactory performance seen in-the-clinic setting analyses, i.e., 0.81/0.82
342 in Iakovakis et al. (2018) and 0.81/0.81 in Arroyo-Gallego et al. (2017). The results are also compliant
343 with the findings of Arroyo-Gallego et al. (2018), who suggests that keystroke dynamics on physical
344 keyboard can be used for remote PD screening with sensitivity/specificity of 0.73/0.69. Estimated indexes
345 were also aggregated across the time frames of hour, weekday, and week, as to compute the variance and
346 consistency of the indices over time. **Figure 6** exemplifies the longitudinal estimates of the median of
347 indices coming from a PD patient and a healthy GData user for hour/weekday and for six continuous weeks
348 of data contribution. Estimated indexes of both subjects have a constant behavior over the time frames of
349 week and weekday, whereas intra day data are more variant.

Figure 6. Responses of the estimated indices across time using different time resolution (hours, weekdays and weeks) of two cases, i.e., a PD (blue graph) and a control (green graph). Blue/green line represents the median of the estimated indices, whereas blue/green dots are estimations for a single typing session regarding the PD patient/control contribution for each period of time.

350 Additionally, in **Figure 7** group-wise comparisons of the time response of the indexes are depicted, with
 351 an obvious discrimination of the two groups across different time frame resolutions. The corresponding
 352 standard deviation of PD/controls; 0.37/0.34 for hours 0.27/0.3 for weekday and 0.24/0.3 for week. The
 353 latter denote more variant behavior during the day rather than the weekday and week for both groups.
 354 In fact, intra-day variations of controls' fine-motor skills have been previously reported (Van Vugt et al.
 355 (2013)) to be affected by the circadian rhythm, which can also be considered as a factor that might influence
 356 the findings here, due to its relation with fine motor movements during smartphone interaction. Also,
 357 dopamine plays a substantial role on circadian regulation and timing behavior (Agostino et al. (2011)),
 358 whereas recent works (Videnovic and Golombek (2017)) present increasing evidence to disruption of
 359 circadian function in PD, where a dopamine-based therapy may increase the circadian oscillations. Healthy
 360 population tends to have the peak of their motor coordination and fast reflexes between the time zone of
 361 14:00 and 16:00 (Bass (2012); Smolensky and Lamberg (2015)), which may explain the groups' median
 362 indexes divergence during that specific period of time, as it can be seen in **Figure 7**. Though circadian
 363 rhythm in PD is a novel area of research and recent studies state it as a new therapeutic target (Videnovic
 364 and Willis (2016)), applications of digital health with interpretability can enhance the understanding of the
 365 underlying patterns of the human behavior, setting the direction for the future work.

366 From a wider perspective, smartphone interaction has been a promising research direction (Pan et al.
 367 (2015)) for detecting individual PD-related symptoms, such as gait difficulties and hand tremor through
 368 accelerometer recordings during the execution of specific scenarios using a smartphone. Furthermore, fusion
 369 of data associated with different PD symptoms captured via smartphone-based tests (Arora et al. (2015))
 370 and machine learning have been explored towards PD screening, resulting in classification performance of
 371 0.96/0.97 sensitivity/specificity. Although the latter study provides proof-of-evidence for the feasibility of
 372 assessing a wide range of motor symptoms through smartphone interaction, data were recorded during
 373 guided scenarios, constraining the scalability of data collection due to the requirement of users' active

Figure 7. Response of the estimated indices across time using δ of (A) daily hours and (B) weekdays, for all subjects grouped according to their health status, i.e., PD (green graph) and controls (blue graph). The solid lines represent the group medians, whereas the shadowed areas denote the upper(75th)/lower(25th) quartiles range, respectively.

374 participation. The novelty of the current study is that it sets up an interpretable framework for unobtrusive
 375 assessment of individual PD symptoms, which can be further used in combination with other data sources,
 376 e.g., background and privacy-aware capturing of accelerometer data for tremor assessment during typing
 377 or microphone data (voice) for dysarthrophonia assessment during phone calls, to broaden symptom
 378 assessment and pave the way for a holistic objective PD detection tool. Following the same approach
 379 proposed in this work, the additional data sources can potentially yield explainable symptom severity
 380 indicators, that if combined, can form a fused behavioral vector based on which the final decision of the
 381 subject's status against PD can be reached, in a similar way that diagnosis takes place in clinical practice.
 382 The fusion approach can include the feeding of the time-aggregated (e.g., every week) behavioral vectors
 383 to a decision system, similar to that of (Arora et al. (2015)), allowing for high frequency monitoring of the
 384 time evolution of both the overall decision, as well as the individual PD symptoms indicators. This is the
 385 direction that the i-PROGNOSIS European research project (www.i-prognosis.eu) follows towards
 386 early PD screening in daily living, in the context of which this study has been carried out.

387 One possible limitation of our study is that patients under dopaminergic therapy that were included in the
388 DSet data setting refrained from taking their medication at least eight hours before their participation in the
389 experiment, instead of the 12 hours that usually secures the “practically off” condition. The latter, combined
390 with potential effects of long-duration response to Levodopa, may have improved the psycho-motor state
391 of these patients and consequently, their typing cadence, leading to a reduced discrimination performance
392 across classification methods tested. Nevertheless, the promising results of the symptoms’ estimation in
393 the DSet setting show limited “echoing” effects of dopaminergic therapy on certain study participants’
394 fine motor skills. A second possible limitation of this study is the validity of the users’ self-reported
395 demographics in the GData data setting. This perhaps will induce noise in the data evaluation. However,
396 using the time-frame of one week within the range of 52 weeks creates a longitudinal user profile at the
397 micro and macro level of analysis, which reveals a data driven behavior that can be compared across
398 different users. In this way, noticeable deviations could lead to group reorganization; yet, this was not the
399 case here.

400 Considering the future adoption and extension of the current methods, effectiveness of the approach will
401 not be affected by subjects’ reorganization because symptoms severity estimators were trained/evaluated
402 based on data captured from a medically valid cohort. However, reorganization could happen to the
403 in-the-wild cohort, which was used for the reporting of diagnostic properties of the indices. The group
404 reorganization will not severely affect the findings, since the diagnostic properties of the indices are
405 reported with a confidence interval, the true value of the diagnostic performance will probably lie in the
406 span of the reported confidence intervals in case of more participants join the study. Moreover, demographic
407 characteristics did not show any statistical significance from the logistic regression tests. Scalability is the
408 main cause the study is designed in this manner, and re-analyzing the data arising from a larger pool of
409 subjects will yield to even more robust values for the diagnostic performance, which will further increase
410 the medical interpretation of the proposed approach. Towards this, research plans include sampling of
411 subjects for medical evaluation in order to fine-tune the time-aggregation function used in this study towards
412 better modeling of time-related variations of the proposed indicators.

413 Regarding the transparency of the developed machine learning methods, the current approach aims to
414 quantify the fine-motor skills of the user and transform daily behavior to indices that can be linked to
415 scores of the physician’s assessments. The produced indices can be also reverse-explained by the physician
416 due to the initial compact feature representation and plausible correlations with standardized UPDRS
417 items. The use of specific features in the pipeline, which are naturally linked to fine-motor impairment,
418 further enhances the interpretability of the resulting estimations. Specifically, keystroke dynamics-related
419 features inputted to the regression mechanisms are naturally affected by rigidity (muscle stiffness) and
420 bradykinesia (slowness of movement), causing longer (mean of HT), more variant (standard deviation of
421 HT) pressings of virtual keyboard keys and slower finger coordination across the screen (skewness of FT),
422 during PD patients’ typing, when compared to controls. The latter can be interpreted by the physician as an
423 objective projection of the scale of symptoms’ severity to the specific body part used to perform the task.
424 In a nutshell, the developed approach aims to support physicians, not replace them, and accelerate the PD
425 diagnosis, by providing objective tools for remote quantification of the symptoms footprint on the patient.

CONCLUSIONS

426 In this study, evidence of real-life usage of unobtrusive detection of fine-motor symptoms from undiagnosed
427 population using prior information on symptoms severity estimation in-the-clinic setting was provided. The
428 presented results validate the initial hypothesis that individual symptom severity can be approximated using

429 keystroke dynamics information and based on this, PD can be detected via keystroke pattern analysis when
430 data are captured in-the-wild. Separation between PD and healthy controls, purely based on smartphone
431 keystroke dynamics is possible and these results could be seen constantly over a longer time frame.
432 Furthermore, the severity expressed by the smartphone touchscreen typing corresponds well with the
433 severity evaluated by the neurologists on which the training algorithms are based. Potential future extension
434 of the method can include the use of deep learning (LeCun et al. (2015)), accompanied with explainable
435 methods (Gunning (2017)), which may reveal better representations of the raw keystroke dynamics and
436 capture more efficiently the latent factors of the symptom's digital footprint, considering also other factors
437 in the analysis, such as the circadian rhythm. Finally, embedding such analyses in the operational systems
438 of smartphones could assist the mobile health booming, considering though, all ethical guidelines and data
439 regulations regarding privacy and security, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

440 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
441 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

442 S.H., V.C., S.B. and Z.K. conceived the study protocol; D.I., S.H. and V.C. developed the keyboard and
443 the algorithms; D.I., S.H. and V.C. conducted the typing experiment; S.B. and Z.K. conducted the clinical
444 evaluations; D.I., S.H., L.H. and V.C. analysed the data; S.H., S.B., Z.K., L.K., H.R., S.D., J.D. D.T. and
445 R.C. developed the GData demographic information, participant information and e-consent process and
446 handled the data governance procedures as well as the corresponding GData ethic approvals. All authors
447 discussed the results and contributed to the manuscript.

FUNDING

448 The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
449 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690494 - i-PROGNOSIS: Intelligent
450 Parkinson early detection guiding novel supportive interventions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

451 The authors wish to acknowledge the donations of time and data from all of the i-PROGNOSIS study
452 participants, engineering contributions from Ntakakis George, Fotis Karayiannis and Kyritsis Konstantinos,
453 for support of the iPrognosis app and data-collection system, proof reading by Anastasia Ntracha.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

454 All data generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on a
455 reasonable request.

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	PD patients	Healthy	Statistical Significance
n (total n = 48)	13	35	N.A.
Demographics			
Women # (%)	5 (38%)	14 (40%)	n.s. (p = 0.92)
Men # (%)	8 (62%)	21 (60%)	n.s. (p = 0.92)
Avg. Age, years (std)	62 (6)	57 (8)	n.s. (p = 0.09)
No. of participants that completed education level E1/E2/E3/E4/E5	0/0/5/7/1	1/1/7/18/8	n.s. (p = 0.08)
No. of participants that used a smartphone for S1/S2 /S3	2/0 /11	4/0/31	n.s. (p = 0.7)

Table 1. Summary of GData study cohort (48 subjects) demographic and clinical characteristics with respect to each group (PD patients and Healthy). Levels of education: E1: 0-8 years in school, E2: 8-10 years in school, E3: > 10 years in school and no other studies, E4: University or college degree, E5: Post graduate degree (master, PhD) Smartphone usage period: S1: < 6 months, S2: 6-12 months, S3: > 12 months N.A.: not applicable; sig.: significant; n.s.: non-significant.

Metrics	Single Metrics			Estimated Indexes	
	HT μ_i	HT σ_i	NFT S_i	RS	BS
AUC, 95% CI	0.76 (0.67-0.86)	0.67 (0.59-0.77)	0.74 (0.62-0.86)	0.84 (0.75-0.93)	0.8 (0.70-0.92)
Sensitivity, 95% CI	0.62 (0.32-0.86)	0.77(0.46-0.95)	0.31 (0.09-0.61)	0.77 (0.46-0.94)	0.92 (0.64-0.99)
Specificity, 95% CI	0.83 (0.66-0.93)	0.71 (0.53-0.85)	0.89 (0.75-0.97)	0.8 (0.63-0.92)	0.63 (0.44-0.78)
Positive Predictive Value, 95% CI	0.57 (0.36-0.75)	0.5 (0.35-0.64)	0.5 (0.22-0.77)	0.59 (0.41-0.74)	0.48 (0.37-0.59)
Negative Predictive Value, 95% CI	0.85 (0.74-0.92)	0.9 (0.70-0.97)	0.79 (0.72-0.84)	0.9 (0.77-0.96)	0.95 (0.76-0.99)
Diagnostic Accuracy, 95% CI	0.77 (0.62-0.87)	0.73 (0.58-0.84)	0.74 (0.60-0.85)	0.79 (0.65-0.89)	0.71 (0.63-0.88)

Table 2. Diagnostic properties of the typing features and the symptoms estimated scores as calculated in the GData cohort. Thresholds were computed by maximizing the Youden Index of the corresponding bootstrapped ROC curves. CI: Confidence Interval; RS: Rigidity Scores, BS: Bradykinesia Scores